
AN OVERVIEW OF NIGERIA’S FOREIGN POLICY DURING THE 2ND REPUBLIC WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO ECOWAS MEMBERSHIP

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Abstract

The foreign policy of a country towards inter-governmental organizations has become a Predominant characteristic in the contemporary world order, and Nigeria is an active member of the international community. Its foreign policy towards Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and its formation in 1975 is examined based on Nigeria’s contributions to the regional organization. The objectives of this article are; to explain the historical background of Nigerian foreign policy during the 2nd Republic; to analyze Nigerian foreign policy approach towards ECOWAS in the 2nd Republic Era; and, finally, to evaluate the strength and weakness of the Nigerian foreign policy in the direction of ECOWAS during 2nd Republic. The application of the content analytical method which was used in this article is to realize the objectives set out in the article and to allow the author give a basic conclusion, mainly that foreign policy is an effective mechanism in projecting a country’s image and policy direction abroad in modern international relations system.

Keywords: ECOWAS, International Community, Policy

Introduction

Every nation on earth, regardless of how strong or developed it is, is not totally self-sufficient. As a result of this, it always strives to achieve its national interest, which is the substance of every nation’s foreign policy.¹ Therefore, states

design their foreign policies in ways that it is geared towards the production and advancement of what constitutes its national interest.² However, the issue of what constitutes Nigeria’s national interest has over the time remained a matter of intense debate among scholars.³ Nevertheless, there are basically four

¹ W. I. Ayodele, S.M. Adeniyi and C.F. Chidozie, “A critical Evolution of Nigeria’s foreign policy at 55”, in covenant University journal of policies and international Affairs Vol. 1 No.2, Ota, Ogun, state. 2013.

² Ibid

³ S. O. Akinboye, Beautiful Abroad but Ugly At Home: Issues and contradictions in Nigeria’s foreign policy.

important elements that characterize Nigeria's national interest, namely:

- ✓ The defence of the country's sovereign, independence territorial wellbeing of its people;
- ✓ The promotion of equality and self-reliance in Africa and the rest of the developing world;
- ✓ The promotion and defense of justice and respect for human dignity, especially the dignity of the black man;
- ✓ The creation of necessary political and economic conditions in Africa and rest of the world which will facilitate the defence of the independence and territorial integrity of all African countries while at the same time fostering national self-reliance and rapid economic development.⁴

Successive regimes and administrations in Nigeria have had their fair share in the experimental process of various foreign policy principles, objectives and strategies.⁵ Given this, the present study attempts to analyze the foreign policy of Nigeria during the second Republic (1979-1983), as well as examine some of its achievements and constraints to the Nigerian state.

⁴ A. Olajide (ed.) Essays on Nigerian foreign policy, George Allen and Unwin Publishers, London 1981.p.264.

⁵ Ibid. p.264-5

Conceptual Clarifications

The term Foreign policy has been variously defined by scholars over time. However, we cannot avoid saying something about the notion of foreign policy in general, and how it is understood in the Nigerian context. The concept of foreign policy has defied a universally acceptable definition. However, for our purpose in this paper, a working definition is needed.

Foreign policy can be defined as the collection of specific policy strategies chosen from a variety of alternatives and implemented over time and space in order to achieve specified set of goals and objectives that would lead the society towards the attainment or protection of prepared values.⁶ This definition suggests that whatever a nation or possibly her leaders choose from a variety of alternatives will be considered as her foreign policy. Similarly, foreign policy of a state usually refers to the general principles by which a state governs its reaction to the international environment.⁷

Moreover, foreign policy can refer to the general objectives that guide the activities and relationships of one

⁶ R.A Akindele, "Foreign policy "in O. Oyidiran, (ed.) introduction to political science. Oyidiran consultant, Ibadan, 2003. p.6.

⁷ C.O. Lerche jr. and Said (eds.), concepts of international politics in Global perspective, Englewood cliffs, 1979.p.32.

state in its interactions with other state. It is also seen as a set of principles that define the objectives a given state pursues in the process of its interactions with other international actors.⁸ For instance, Nigeria's repeated attempts to put an end to the conflicts in Chad during 1979 and early 1980 as well as the remarkable role the country played in ending the racial apartheid regime in south Africa are perfect examples here. In a nutshell therefore, it could be concluded from the foregoing definitions that the country's foreign policy since independence has usually been formulated in line with the national interests of the federation and that of the citizens.

The Second Republic

In Nigerian political history, the second Republic refers to the period between October 1979 to August 1983 which led to the emergence of Nigeria's first democratically elected president since the military coup of January 1966. On 1st October, 1979, after about thirteen (13) years of military rule, Alhaji Shehu Shagari was sworn in as president, alongside his vice, Chief Alexander Ekweme,⁹ in a regime that ended with the

military intervention of 31st August, 1983.

Background of Nigeria's Foreign Policy under President Shehu Shagari

The election in 1979 was held in a relatively calm condition. It was won by the National Party of Nigeria (NPN), a northern-based political party which drew support from Yoruba, Igbo and other minority groups as well.¹⁰ Although the NPN did not meet the two third majority of the 19 states criterium required by the electoral body, Shagari was eventually declared winner of the election, leading to minor disagreement over the results.¹¹

When Shagari came on board after about thirteen years of military rule, he inherited a foreign policy that required firmness and dynamism because it focused on issues such as decolonization and independence struggle for African countries like Namibia and Zimbabwe; fight against the apartheid regime in south Africa; conflict resolution in the Libya – Chadian civil war; Cameroon;

⁸ See Aluko O" (ed.) Essays on Nigerian foreign policy. Op cit. p.263

⁹ A. B Akinyemi, S.O. Agbi and A.O Otubajo (eds), Nigeria since independence: international

Relations – the First 25years. Vol.X., Heinemann Educational Book, Lagos, 1989.p.40

¹⁰ M. Meredith, the state of Africa: A History of the continent since independence, Simon and Schuster Ltd., London, 2011. P.220

¹¹Ibid.I

border conflict in 1981; Nigeria – US relations among other issues.¹²

It is pertinent to state that despite some of the successes recorded by the Shagari administration, it was plagued by series of irreconcilable crises ranging from inflation, constant cases of corrupt practices, inter and intra-party squabble to agitations from trade unions and civil society group.¹³ For example, the Nigeria Labour congress, (NLC), strike in 1981 which led to the description of the regime as ‘inept’ and ‘highly corrupt’.¹⁴ Agriculture was further neglected, leading to dependence on oil revenue due to the oil boom of the 1970s and early 1980s. This brought about the increase in the importation of numerous goods into the country by the elites, leading to a collapse in local industries. Nigeria would become a rentier state, thereby creating a negative implication for the content and nature of Nigeria’s foreign policy.

Nigeria’s Foreign Policy during the Shagari Regime

In some significant ways as stated, Nigeria’s relations with the superpowers during the Shagari era

¹² A.J Omede *Nigeria’s Relations with Her Neighbors*, Kamlaraj publisher Ltd., London, 2006.p.12.

¹³ L. Adamolekun, *the fall of the second Republic* Spectrum Book Ltd., Ibadan, 1985.p.88-89.

¹⁴ *Ibid.* p.89

represented a carry-over from the earlier regimes. President Shagari, in a sense, was a product of the Tafawa Balewa administration under which he served as a Parliamentary secretary. He therefore largely reflected the personality and projected the ethos of that epoch.¹⁵ He had also served as a minister in Gowon’s government and had immediately succeeded the highly dynamic and military aggressive Murtala/Obasanjo regime.¹⁶ The foreign policy objectives inherited by Shagari in the 1979 constitution were as follows:

- The state shall promote African unity
- It shall promote total political, economic, social and cultural liberation of Africa.
- Its shall promote all other forms of international cooperation conducive to the consolidation of universal peace and mutual respect and friendship among all peoples and state.
- It shall combat any form of racial discrimination in all its manifestation.

In reinstatement of the above constitutional provision, in his maiden address to the National Assembly on 16th October 1979, the President stated that:

¹⁵ A. B. Akinyemi, S.O. Agbi and A.O. Otubajo (eds.), *Nigeria since independence; international Relations- the First 25years*, vol.x Henemann Educational Book, Lagos, 1989.p.67.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

In foreign policy, Africa still remains our primary interest. We renew our pledge of support to ECOWAS, the OAU and the liberation movement of Africa. It be known that our commitment to the total liberation of our brothers in Zimbabwe, Namibia and South Africa remains unshaken.¹⁷

Because of this commitment in ensuring Africa as the centre peace of Nigeria's foreign policy, Shagari made important trips in search for solution to the conflict in North Africa which had erupted as the result of claim over the ownership of Western Sahara between the Moroccan forces and the Spanish government in the 1960s.¹⁸ The president's pledge to the decolonization of Africa was glaring when he organized and hosted the African Economic Summit in Lagos under the aegis of the Organization of African Unity (OAU)

¹⁷ Y.E Ihugh and K.p Memba. "Redefining Nigeria's foreign policy within the context of modern Day security challenge" in ATim (ed) Africa: Dynamism of Social science Research, vol.4 No 1 june 2013, at-Mishad publisher, Makurdi, 2013.p.48

¹⁸ E.N Mord. "The western sahara conflict: the Dilemma of National Liberation War, Referendum , and terrorism in Africa's Last Colony, 1973-2013" international Rewiew of Social sciences and hummanities vol. 9. No.1. Delta state University, Abraka, 2015. P.3.

known as the Lagos plan of Action in 1980s.¹⁹

The 1979 constitution which was organized and largely influenced by the previous Mohammed/Obasanjo regime signified the high level of political and psychological unity which had existed between Nigeria and the United States.²⁰ Under Shagari therefore, the presidential constitution provided the first reason for continuing and even intensifying the fraternal relations between the countries.²¹ This is why many elected Representatives, senators and other officials made frequent pilgrimage to the United States to study the presidential system of government there.

The favorable American image in the country allowed Shagari to maintain and improve relations with the United States in many other areas. Apart from the traditional oil-sector connection, the Shagari administration made special efforts to intensify economic intercourse and cooperation with US in the areas of agriculture, especially after launching its

¹⁹ See. Ibid...p.48-49

²⁰ A. Okolo. "Nigeria and the superpowers", in A. B Akinyemi, S.O. Agbi A.O Otunbanjo(eds.), Nigeria since independence: international Relations – the first 25 years, Volume x. Heinemann Educational Books Ltd...Ibadan, 1989. P.67.

²¹Ibid

Green Revolution programme.²² A United States Nigeria Joint Agricultural Consultative Committee (JACC) was formed to facilitate the sale of American agricultural products and machinery. Consequently Nigeria's non-oil export and import from that country also increased considerably.²³

Shagari sustained the policy of Mohammed/Obasanjo especially in the area of the Liberation Movement. For example, Shagari followed up the earlier regime's firm support for the struggle in Zimbabwe with a ten million dollars grant to President Mugabe during their independence celebration in April 1980. The amount was to be used to acquire the Zimbabwe Herald from racist South Africa.²⁴

However, America continued to remain intensive to Africa's efforts to achieve immediate change in Southern Africa, especially the Ronald Regan Administration from 1981 which tried to stall Namibian independence by supporting Jonas Savimbi and thereby tried to reverse the achievements of the Mohammed/Obasanjo administration. Regan met serious opposition from

Shagari who was out protecting the policies of his predecessor in this area.²⁵

The administration's relation with the Soviets remained normal and cordial.²⁶ Since the Balewa era, and especially after the experiences of the civil War, Nigerian perception of the Soviets had considerably changed for the better.²⁷ The Soviets had proved consistent and steady allies in Nigeria's efforts to eradicate racism and apartheid in southern Africa. Therefore, in spite of the fact that economic relations between these countries remained unavoidably low as usual, during his period in office, Shagari continued to rely heavily on the Soviets' support for the Liberation Movements.²⁸

Nigeria's relation with Britain changed politically during this period, especially with the emergence of an American-typed of presidential democracy because Britain would have preferred the continuation of the British parliamentary system of government in Nigeria.²⁹ However, the issues that could not have bought Nigeria and Britain into

²² A. Okolo. "Nigeria and the Superpowers", in A.B Akinyemi, S.Oagbi, A.O Otubanjo (eds.), op cit.p

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ A. Okolo "Nigeria and the superpowers", in A.B Akinyemi, S.O Agbi, and A.O Otubanjo (eds.) opcit.p.68

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ See, R. Legvold, soviet policy in West Africa, Harvard University press, Cambridge, 1970. P.3-10

²⁹ A.B. Akinyemi, foreign policy and federalism. Ibadan University press, Ibadan, 1974.p.36-38.

conflict with each other during the Second Republic.³⁰

The vents occurring within some African countries like Namibia, South Africa and Cameroon must have shaped the decision of Shagari's regime. At that period, Namibia and South African were struggling to liberate themselves from the shackles of colonialism and Racism. The Cameroonian border dispute of 1981 was also an incident that drove Nigeria's interest towards continuous works with its other African countries not as rich and free as it was during the period under study.³¹

Strengths and Weaknesses of the second Republic foreign policy

Nigeria, under the Shagari foreign policy played a major role and held a hard line position in the southern African statehood in April 1980. Under the Shagari regime, crude petroleum continued to be sold at consolatory prices to a number of poor African countries. Financial aid was also given to others like newly independent Zimbabwe and some other organization like South West African Parliamentary Organization (SWAPO) in Namibia. A remarkable political understanding between Nigeria and the Soviets was strengthened during

Shagari is regime to the extent that Soviets proved to be a steady and reliable ally that could be called upon to aid, something that had become an essential identification of the Shagari regime.³²

However, having inherited a foreign policy that required firmness and dynamism, Shagari was perceived to be weak and indecisive. This may be so due to the perception by some people that he got the mantle of leadership without intense struggle and suffering.³³ His decision to work with foreign policy objectives of past regime could have been driven by that purpose. These, alongside several other allegations were used as justifications of his overthrow from office by the military in 1983.

Nigeria's foreign policy under Shagari's regime suffered from strained relationship with other countries like Ghana when it expelled aliens mostly from Ghana in 1983. That singular act questioned Nigeria's spirit of brotherhood and the Economic Community of West African States

³⁰ Ibid.p.38.

³¹ See A.J Omede. Nigeria's Relations with Her Neighbors, op cit....p.15

³² Y.E Ihugh and K.P Mema, "Redefining Nigeria's foreign policy within the context of modern-day Security challenge" in T. Atim (ed) Africa: Dynamism of social sciences research vol4, no 1 June 2013, at-mishad Macmillan press, London, 1982. History notes.

³³ For an elaboration on the weakness of the second republic. See for example. L Adamolekun, the Fall of the Second Republic opcit.p.89

(ECOWAS) Treaty.³⁴ Foreign policy in the period of Shagari's administration experienced a radical departure from the prevailing pattern of the previous administration, as Nigeria's external policy came to assume a low profile like that which was obtained under Balewa's regime. As Balewa, the nature and character of the president Shehu Shagari was very conservative.³⁵

Internal crisis and domestic policies always have an adverse effect on the foreign policy of countries, Nigeria which is not an exemption was also affected by internal policies and domestic crises that affected its foreign policy decisions and strategies. For example, the weakness of the ruling class, vested interests, the problem of being a renter state, inter and intra party rivalry, inconsistency in policy execution, poverty, endemic corruption economic recession, alienation, political instability, rural decay, agricultural stagnation, inefficiency, misuse of state power and mismanagement of oil rents had all played a significant role and had effect on Nigeria's foreign policy initiatives and action.

³⁴ A.j omede Nigeria's Relations with her Neighbors op.cit.....

³⁵ L. Adamolekum the fall of the second republic opcit.....p.89

Conclusion

From independence in 1960 to date, Nigeria has witnessed numerous regimes and their attempts to form their foreign policy towards achieving what they refer to as "Nigeria's National interest". However, successive regimes have continued to face the problem of defining the truly National interest of Nigeria. Nigerian successive regimes have also been faced with the problem of inconsistency in foreign policy objectives and attitude of policy reversal which has weakened its role in international politics. Until successive regimes get consistent with the core objectives of Nigerian foreign policy, then things are likely to continue the way they are or even exacerbate.

The Nigerian policy makers need to be fully involved in the formulation of foreign policies that are not rigid or based solely on their personal disposition and in the interest of a few elites in the society while connecting the effect it would have on majority of citizens within the country. The Shagari regime was marred by empty promises and rhetorics bringing about an inconclusive and inactive foreign policy strategy that failed in many remarkable instances.

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